

Real-Time Regulator Optimization for Tip-Tilt Compensation on Extremely Large Telescopes

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ABSTRACT

Next generation ground-based telescopes like the Extremely Large Telescope (ELT) will face new challenges related to the increasing size of the device, the number of actuators, and the complexity of the control system. One of the phenomena that is more likely to impact the performance of such devices is the vibration of the telescope structure due to the wind or ground motion. This affects the low-order modes of aberration, in particular Tip and Tilt modes in the Zernike basis. We present a real-time gain adaptation strategy for Tip-Tilt correction in Adaptive Optics systems, designed to address the dynamics evolution and noise characteristics inherent to the observation process. The method proposes a dynamic optimization framework for tuning the digital regulator transfer function to minimize the temporal residual wavefront error variance in closed-loop control. A constrained, multivariable, quadratic optimization problem is formulated to obtain the desired performance while ensuring stability of the closed loop system. The minimization problem is solved in a predictive control scheme, by integrating an identification step of the exosystem describing the temporal evolution of the Tip-Tilt distortion due to the windshake. The approach is particularly suitable for astronomical Adaptive Optics scenarios with changing measurement conditions, as the signal-to-noise ratio is dependent on the selected guide star, and variable atmospheric and observation conditions, thus offering a robust and flexible alternative to manual tuning. Moreover, it exhibits more flexibility with respect to the robust design of a static gain or model dependent gain scheduling.

Keywords: Adaptive Optics, ELT, Optimization, Closed-loop Control

1. INTRODUCTION

Next generation telescopes may feature a primary mirror with a diameter of about 40 meters that can capture more light and image fainter objects than before [13][6]. Due to their size, these devices are likely to experience vibrations caused by wind shaking the telescope structure [7] [12]. These vibrations cause tip and tilt modes of aberrations, leading to a significant degradation of the image quality [10]. Tip-tilt aberrations are expected to be the most significant error source for Extremely Large Telescopes (ELTs). In this work, an optimization strategy is proposed for a filter designed to reject tip and tilt distortion in an Adaptive Optics (AO) loop, while limiting high-frequency noise propagation. The optimization problem is formulated in the time domain, with the goal of

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Figure 1. Closed loop AO system for tip/tilt compensation.

minimizing the output residual phase variance. In the scenario accounted by this paper, a pre-defined Infinite Impulse Response (IIR) filter is considered, and the gain of the filter is optimized. The IIR filter will be adopted for tip-tilt correction on MORFEO (Agapito, G. et al. 2026, Manuscript in preparation), because it allows to reject the low-frequency components of the disturbance while mitigating the high-frequency noise amplification. The goal of the gain optimization process is to finely tune the cut-off bandwidth of the closed-loop sensitivity transfer function, based on open-loop disturbance data (or a reconstructed history of it). The optimization problem can be solved online, as data are acquired, or offline, assuming the frequency properties of the disturbance are well known and time-invariant. The offline gain optimization approach is affine to the one presented in [5], where it is shown how an optimal trade-off gain exists to minimize the residual error at a given modal order while amplifying the measurement noise. In this work, the exosystem generating the disturbance is explicitly identified from data, and the optimization problem is formulated in a state-space framework. This approach allows accounting for a possibly time-varying nature of the disturbance which may benefit of the online adaption of the regulator gain which is described in the paper. A scalar optimization problem is finally formulated, and solved using the method in [1], as a derivative-free optimization method for scalar constrained problems. The proposed approach is finally tested in SPECULA [11], an end-to-end simulator for AO systems, both in its offline and online applications, in a simplified framework where no higher order modes are considered to be propagated in the control loop. The optimization approach of this work is well-suited for the control problem of the ELTs which suffer from wind shake induced vibrations. In particular, it has been developed in the context of the MORFEO (Multiconjugate adaptive Optics Relay For ELT Observations) project. [3]

The paper is organized as follows. In section 2, the optimization problem is presented in a general framework. In section 3, the gain optimization problem is formulated, and in section 4 the identification procedure of the exosystem generating the wind-shake distortion is described. The offline and online applications of the optimization approach are discussed in section 5. Finally, in section 6, simulation results are presented and discussed.

2. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The problem of optimizing the tip and tilt regulator is formulated as a discrete time optimization problem. The closed loop AO system for tip-tilt compensation is represented in figure 1. At each time step t , the goal is to minimize the squared sum of the residual phase samples in the optimization horizon T :

$$J(\theta) = \sum_{\tau=t}^{t+T} \|y_{\tau}\|_2^2, \quad (1)$$

The dynamics of the system is described by the state-space equations of the closed loop scheme.

$$\begin{aligned} x_{\tau+1} &= \mathcal{A}(\theta)x_{\tau} + \mathcal{B}(\theta)\Phi_{\tau}, \\ y_{\tau} &= \mathcal{C}(\theta)x_{\tau} + \mathcal{D}(\theta)\Phi_{\tau}, \quad \tau = t, \dots, t+T-1 \\ x_t &= \bar{x}_t, \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

being $\{\Phi_{\tau} \in \mathbb{R}^2\}_{\tau \in \mathbb{N}}$ the sequence of tip/tilt samples. In this formulation, state-space matrices $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{C}, \mathcal{D}$ are a realization of the closed-loop transfer matrix $G(z) = Y(z)\Phi(z)^{-1}$; meaning that:

$$G(z) = \mathcal{C}(zI - \mathcal{A})^{-1}\mathcal{B} + \mathcal{D}, \quad (3)$$

therefore, they are functions of the regulator transfer function $R(z, \theta)$. The vector of parameters $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^N$ describes the regulator transfer matrix, which is optimized to minimize $J(\theta)$, and vector $x_{\tau} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the internal state of the closed loop system. If the same regulator is adopted for tip and tilt and it is an IIR filter of order k , $\theta \in \mathbb{R}^{2k+1}$

contains k zeros, k poles and the gain of the filter. In this first representation of the problem, performance output y_τ is a vector in \mathbb{R}^2 , containing the amplitude of the modal coefficients for tip and tilt.

In this work, the optimization problem is approached for a single mode, the input exogenous signal Φ is a scalar signal and the performance output y is a scalar quantity as well. The extension of the proposed approach to a multivariable framework is straightforward, and will be introduced at the end of section 5. In the simulations, the same controller is adopted for both tip and tilt, so that the problem is effectively solved for a single mode. With these considerations, the plant is a single-input-single-output system, and we will consider the transfer function from $\Phi \in \mathbb{R}$ to $y \in \mathbb{R}$. The state space dynamics can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} x_{\tau+1} &= A(\theta)x_\tau + B(\theta)\Phi_\tau, \\ y_\tau &= C(\theta)x_\tau + D(\theta)\Phi_\tau, \quad \tau = t, \dots, t+T-1 \\ x_t &= \bar{x}_t, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Matrices $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$, $C \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n}$ represent the state-space description of the closed loop system, including the plant, that is, the wavefront sensor and the deformable mirror dynamics, where n represents the order of a minimal realization of the system. In the analysis for the present work, the state-space matrices have been computed as the realization, in canonical controllable form, of the closed loop transfer function:

$$G(z) = \frac{\text{WFS}(z)}{1 + \text{WFS}(z)R(z, \theta)\text{DM}(z)}. \quad (5)$$

Matrix D , mapping the input to the output, does not exist in a physical realization of the adaptive optics system, because a loop delay always exists.

By forward propagating the dynamics, the residual wavefront signal for a single mode is:

$$y_\tau = C(\theta)A(\theta)^{\tau-t}x_t + \sum_{i=0}^{\tau-t-1} C(\theta)A(\theta)^{\tau-t-1-i}B(\theta)\Phi_{t+i}, \quad \tau = t, \dots, t+T, \quad (6)$$

The optimization problem can be formulated as an unconstrained optimization problem in the parameter space θ as follows:

$$\min_{\theta} \sum_{\tau=t}^{t+T} y_\tau^2 = \min_{\theta} \sum_{\tau=t}^{t+T} \left(C(\theta)A(\theta)^{\tau-t}x_t + \sum_{i=0}^{\tau-t-1} C(\theta)A(\theta)^{\tau-t-1-i}B(\theta)\Phi_{t+i} \right)^2. \quad (7)$$

In the following section, the optimization of the gain of a pre-defined filter is presented in detail.

3. GAIN OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

Let us define $\bar{R}(z)$, a pre-defined filter, the gain g of which should be chosen optimally to minimize the residual wavefront distortion variance. The overall controller is then $R(z) = g\bar{R}(z)$. The optimization problem (7) is reformulated as:

$$\min_g \sum_{\tau=t}^{t+T} \left(C(g)A(g)^{\tau-t}x_t + \sum_{i=0}^{\tau-t-1} C(g)A(g)^{\tau-t-1-i}B(g)\Phi_{t+i} \right)^2, \quad (8)$$

The optimization problem, in this case, is a scalar (possibly nonlinear) optimization problem. A simple model of the closed-loop system can be defined by assuming that the wavefront sensor is capable of directly measure the modal coefficients of the incoming wavefront, and its only dynamics involves a fixed measurement delay s . It is common [8] [9] to assume that also the deformable mirror introduces a simple delay in the loop, as if the DM was able to perfectly assume the required shape in a finite number of sampling steps c . In this case, the closed loop transfer function can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} G(z) &= \frac{z^{-s}}{1 + z^{-s}R(z)z^{-c}} = \frac{z^{-s}}{1 + z^{-s}g\bar{R}(z)z^{-c}} = \\ &= \frac{z^{-s}}{1 + gz^{-s}\frac{\bar{N}(z)}{\bar{D}(z)}z^{-c}} = \frac{z^{-s}\bar{D}(z)}{\bar{D}(z) + g\bar{N}(z)z^{-(s+c)}}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Let

$$\bar{R}(z) = \frac{\bar{N}(z)}{\bar{D}(z)} = \frac{a_0 + a_1z^{-1} + a_2z^{-2}}{b_0 + b_1z^{-1} + b_2z^{-2}}$$

be the assigned (pre-tuned) IIR regulator for tilt compensation in the SISO system 1. The state-space realization of $G(z)$ in controllable canonical form is:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -a_2 \cdot g/b_0 & -a_1 \cdot g/b_0 & -a_0 \cdot g/b_0 & 0 & -b_2/b_0 & -b_1/b_0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad C = [0 \quad 1 \quad b_1/b_0 \quad b_2/b_0 \quad 0 \quad 0].$$

With our assumptions, only matrix A depends explicitly on g . The optimization problem (8) can be rewritten as:

$$\min_g \sum_{\tau=t}^{t+T} \left(CA(g)^{\tau-t} x_t + \sum_{i=0}^{\tau-t-1} CA(g)^{\tau-t-1-i} B \Phi_{i+\tau} \right)^2. \quad (11)$$

It should also be noticed that the particular choice of the controllable canonical form leads to a structure of matrix $A = A_1 + gA_2$. This allows to rewrite the unconstrained optimization problem (11) as:

$$\min_g \sum_{\tau=t}^{t+T} \left(C(A_1 + gA_2)^{\tau-t} x_t + \sum_{i=0}^{\tau-t-1} C(A_1 + gA_2)^{\tau-t-1-i} B \Phi_{i+\tau} \right)^2. \quad (12)$$

Even if the problem is unconstrained, the solution of (12) requires the computation of T matrix powers of A and to find the roots of a polynomial of order $2T$ in g . This is computationally inconvenient. In the paper, the problem has been solved for the following constrained formulation, which also allows including a constraint on the gain g to ensure the stability of the closed loop system:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_g \sum_{\tau=t}^{t+T} y_\tau^2 &= \sum_{\tau=t}^{t+T} x_\tau^T C^T C x_\tau \\ \text{s.t.} & \\ y_\tau &= C x_\tau, & \tau = t, \dots, t+T \\ x_{\tau+1} &= A_1 x_\tau + A_2 g x_\tau + B \Phi_\tau, \\ g &\in [g_{min}, g_{max}] \\ x_\tau &= \bar{x}_\tau. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The optimization problem can be interpreted as an optimal control problem in which an optimal state feedback policy $u_\tau = g x_\tau$ has to be computed. A better posed optimization problem, in an optimal control sense, would also include a penalization term on the control input.

$$\begin{aligned} \min_g \sum_{\tau=t}^{t+T} (x_\tau^T C^T C x_\tau) + \rho g^2 \\ \text{s.t.} \\ y_\tau &= C x_\tau, & \tau = t, \dots, t+T \\ x_{\tau+1} &= A_1 x_\tau + A_2 g x_\tau + B \Phi_\tau, \\ g &\in [g_{min}, g_{max}] \\ x_\tau &= \bar{x}_\tau \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

with $\rho > 0$. In the formulation above, the problem can be solved if the sequence of wind-shake disturbance samples $\{\Phi_\tau\}_{\tau=t}^{t+T}$ is known over the optimization horizon. This is in fact not the case in a real-time application, where at most noisy past samples of the residual wavefront error can be reconstructed.

Figure 2. Sensitivity transfer function with varying gain.

In the following section, we present the identification step for the exosystem generating the disturbance, with the idea of building a model of the disturbance dynamics from past data, and being able to generate synthetic data for the optimization problem from a class of signals that have frequency properties coherent with those of the input disturbance. In fact, the whole optimization process can be thought as finding the optimal bandwidth of the sensitivity given the frequency content of the disturbance. Figure 2 shows the sensitivity transfer function for different values of the gain g using the following IIR filter:

$$\bar{R}(z) = \frac{(z - 0.45)(z - 0.85)}{(z - 1)(z - 0.9995)}. \quad (15)$$

The IIR filter is better posed in the wind shake affected scenarios with respect to the classical integrator controller, as it better rejects the low-frequency high-power content of the disturbance. The two zeros in the transfer function are placed to limit the propagation of high-frequency measurement noise (Agapito, G. et al. 2026, Manuscript in preparation). Changing the gain leads to a shift in the cut-off frequency of the sensitivity function.

In the paper, the problem of reconstructing open loop data from noisy closed loop measurements is not addressed, and it is assumed that at least a history of wind-shake induced tip-tilt signal is available for training.

4. EXOSYSTEM IDENTIFICATION

The exosystem is identified as an autoregressive (AR) model of order N , fitted on the available data through the least squares approach. The autoregressive model dynamics can be written as:

$$\Phi_\tau = \sum_{i=1}^N a_i \Phi_{\tau-i} + w_\tau, \quad (16)$$

where a_i are the AR coefficients, and $w_\tau \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_w^2)$ is a white noise process.

The autoregressive model can be embedded in a state-space framework as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} v_{\tau+1} &= \tilde{A}v_\tau + \tilde{B}w_\tau, \\ \Phi_\tau &= \tilde{C}v_\tau \\ w_\tau &\sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_w^2), \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where $v_\tau = [\Phi_\tau, \Phi_{\tau-1}, \dots, \Phi_{\tau-N+1}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^N$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} v_{\tau+1} &= \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & a_2 & \dots & a_{N-1} & a_N \\ 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} v_\tau + \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} w_\tau, \\ \Phi_\tau &= [1 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0] v_\tau, \\ w_\tau &\sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_w^2). \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

Figure 3. Comparison between the PSD of the input disturbance and the PSD of the synthetic disturbance generated by the identified autoregressive model.

Figure 4. Comparison between the disturbance and the synthetic tilt signal in time.

The state space matrices of the exosystem can be thus defined as follows.

$$\tilde{A} = \begin{bmatrix} a_1 & a_2 & \dots & a_{N-1} & a_N \\ 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \tilde{B} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \tilde{C} = [1 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0]. \quad (19)$$

Where $\tilde{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$, $\tilde{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 1}$, $\tilde{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times N}$. The model here described was trained on a sequence of wind-shake induced tilt data, obtained from a finite element analysis of the M2 mirror of the ELT [4]. The least square fitting procedure is performed in the following way. Let us define the vector of data samples $\Phi = [\Phi_1, \Phi_2, \dots, \Phi_M]^T$ and the vector of unknowns $\mathbf{a} = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_N]^T$, where M is the number of available samples and N is the order of the autoregressive model. The AR coefficients can be computed as:

$$\mathbf{a}^* = \arg \min_{\mathbf{a}} \|\Phi - V\mathbf{a}\|_2^2, \quad (20)$$

where $V \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}$ is the regression matrix, defined as:

$$V = \begin{bmatrix} \Phi_0 & \Phi_{-1} & \dots & \Phi_{-N+1} \\ \Phi_1 & \Phi_0 & \dots & \Phi_{-N+2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \Phi_{M-1} & \Phi_{M-2} & \dots & \Phi_{M-N} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (21)$$

The solution is given by the normal equations:

$$\mathbf{a}^* = (V^T V)^{-1} V^T \Phi. \quad (22)$$

As discussed, changing the gain of an IIR filter leads to a change in the cut-off frequency of the closed loop sensitivity function. In this sense, it is sufficient, for the identification step, to catch the main frequency components of the disturbance, even if the exact temporal prediction is not accurate. A first result is reported in figure 3, showing the PSD of the tilt disturbance compared with the PSD of a synthetic disturbance, generated with the identified autoregressive model fed with a white noise process. The autoregressive model order was set to $N = 20$, and it catches the main frequency peaks of the disturbance. In figure 4 a synthetic tilt history is shown. The temporal evolution does not match the real disturbance; however, the fact that the frequency content is captured suggests that a class of signals compatible with the input wind-shake disturbance can be generated. The problem of *synchronizing* the synthetic disturbance with the real one is not relevant for the gain optimization process, as the goal is to find the optimal bandwidth for a class of signals having specific frequency properties, rather than for a specific realization of the disturbance. It should be noticed that the identification as an autoregressive model with additive noise introduces stochasticity in the disturbance model. The optimization problem (11) should then

be interpreted as a stochastic optimization problem.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min_g \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{\tau=t}^{t+T} (x_\tau^T C^T C x_\tau) + \rho g^2 \right] \\
& \text{s.t.} \\
& y_\tau = C x_\tau, \\
& v_{\tau+1} = \tilde{A} v_\tau + \tilde{B} w_\tau, \\
& \Phi_\tau = \tilde{C} v_\tau + w_\tau \\
& x_{\tau+1} = A_1 x_\tau + A_2 g x_\tau + B \Phi_\tau, \\
& x_\tau = \bar{x}_\tau, \\
& g \in [g_{min}, g_{max}] \\
& w_\tau \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_w^2 I).
\end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

A way of solving the stochastic optimization problem is computing the empirical mean of the cost function over H realizations, generated with a set of H simulations, with randomized generation of the noise sequences. The expected value of the cost function can then be approximated as follows.

$$\mathbb{E}[J(g)] \approx \frac{1}{H} \sum_{j=1}^H J_j(g), \tag{24}$$

where $J_j(g)$ is the cost function computed for the j -th realization of the disturbance.

5. ON-LINE AND OFF-LINE OPTIMIZATION

The optimization of the gain can be ideally performed in a receding horizon fashion, by solving the optimization problem at each time step t , but this is reasonably too demanding from a computational point of view for the real time computer. A more practical approach is to solve the optimization problem every K time steps, keeping the gain constant in between two optimization steps. This allows to reduce the computational burden of the optimization process, at the cost of a slower adaptation of the gain to changing disturbance characteristics. The main limitation with the online optimization is that open-loop data of the disturbance are needed to perform the identification step and catch the time-varying nature of the disturbance. If we assume that the disturbance has time-invariant dynamics, the optimization problem can be solved offline, generating a history of tip-tilt from the a-priori knowledge of the system dynamics, or from an off-line identified AR model. In this case, the optimization problem can be solved once for all, and the optimal gain g^* can be used in the closed loop system without further adaptations. The optimization problem, in such case, would be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min_g \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{\tau=0}^{\infty} (x_\tau^T C^T C x_\tau) + \rho g^2 \right] \\
& \text{s.t.} \\
& y_\tau = C x_\tau, \\
& v_{\tau+1} = \tilde{A} v_\tau + \tilde{B} w_\tau, \\
& \Phi_\tau = \tilde{C} v_\tau + w_\tau, \\
& x_{\tau+1} = A_1 x_\tau + A_2 g x_\tau + B \Phi_\tau \\
& x_\tau = \bar{x}_\tau, \\
& g \in [g_{min}, g_{max}] \\
& w_\tau \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_w^2 I)
\end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

In case measurement noise is present and propagated through the loop, the optimization problem can be changed to include the state-space realization of the complementary sensitivity function T , defined as follows:

$$T(z) = \frac{R(z)DM(z)WFS(z)}{1 + R(z)DM(z)WFS(z)} = \frac{g\bar{R}(z)DM(z)WFS(z)}{1 + g\bar{R}(z)DM(z)WFS(z)}. \tag{26}$$

Let us define A_η, B_η, C_η the state-space matrices of the complementary sensitivity function $T(z)$ in controllable canonical form. The measurement noise n_τ can be modeled as a white noise process, filtered by the complementary

sensitivity function, so that the overall measurement noise is $C_\eta \eta_\tau$, where η_τ is the state of noise transmission dynamics, evolving as $\eta_{\tau+1} = A_\eta \eta_\tau + B_\eta n_\tau$. The optimization problem (23) can be reformulated, on-line, as:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min_g \mathbb{E} \left[\sum_{\tau=t}^{t+T} (x_\tau^T C^T C x_\tau) + \rho g^2 \right] \\
& \text{s.t.} \\
& y_\tau = C x_\tau + C_\eta \eta_\tau, \\
& v_{\tau+1} = \tilde{A} v_\tau + \tilde{B} w_\tau, \\
& \Phi_\tau = \tilde{C} v_\tau + w_\tau, \quad \tau = t, t+1, \dots, t+T \\
& \eta_{\tau+1} = A_\eta(g) \eta_\tau + B_\eta(g) n_\tau, \\
& x_{\tau+1} = A_1 x_\tau + A_2 g x_\tau + B \Phi_\tau, \\
& x_\tau = \bar{x}_\tau, \\
& g \in [g_{min}, g_{max}] \\
& w_\tau \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_w^2 I) \\
& n_\tau \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_n^2).
\end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

The variance of the measurement noise σ_n^2 partly depends on the brightness of the source, and on the exposure time of the wavefront sensor. The infinite horizon version of the problem is formulated analogously to (25), also considering the propagation of measurement noise. The problem can be solved numerically, relying on standard optimization algorithms for scalar functions with box constraints [1]. The online stochastic problem (27) is useful when the disturbance characteristics are time-varying, a history of wind-shake induced tip-tilt data is not available, but data can be recorded or reconstructed in real-time to perform the identification step. Up to now, the gain optimization for a single channel has been considered. The framework can be extended to a vectorial formulation to optimize over both tip and tilt. The disturbance vector can be defined as $\Phi_\tau = [\Phi_\tau^{tilt}, \Phi_\tau^{tip}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$, and the exosystem would be a MIMO system, with two outputs. The identification step would involve fitting two different autoregressive models on the tip and tilt data, leading to a block diagonal state-space representation of the exosystem, replicating the structure (19) in the two channels with different parameters. The optimization problems would remain unchanged, except for the dimension of the disturbance vector. If we call $\tilde{A}_{tilt}, \tilde{B}_{tilt}, \tilde{C}_{tilt}$ and $\tilde{A}_{tip}, \tilde{B}_{tip}, \tilde{C}_{tip}$ the state-space matrices of the exosystem for tilt and tip, the overall state-space representation of the augmented system, including the dynamics of the disturbance, would be:

$$\begin{aligned}
\begin{bmatrix} v_{\tau+1}^{tilt} \\ v_{\tau+1}^{tip} \\ x_{\tau+1} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{A}_{tilt} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \tilde{A}_{tip} & 0 \\ \tilde{\mathcal{B}}\tilde{C}_{tilt} & \tilde{\mathcal{B}}\tilde{C}_{tip} & \mathcal{A} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_\tau^{tilt} \\ v_\tau^{tip} \\ x_\tau \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{B}_{tilt} & 0 \\ 0 & \tilde{B}_{tip} \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} w_\tau^{tilt} \\ w_\tau^{tip} \end{bmatrix}, \\
y_\tau &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \mathcal{C} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_\tau^{tilt} \\ v_\tau^{tip} \\ x_\tau \end{bmatrix},
\end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

where $\mathcal{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{2n \times 2n}$, $\mathcal{B} \in \mathbb{R}^{2n \times 2}$, and $\mathcal{C} \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2n}$ are the state-space matrices of the AO loop in the vectorial formulation for the two channels. The measurement noise can be included analogously, by augmenting the state-space representation of the complementary sensitivity function for the two channels.

6. SIMULATIONS

The simulation campaign has been performed to test the effectiveness of the gain optimization approach in the online and offline scenarios. The data adopted for identification and optimization is a 15 seconds history of tilt and tip wind-shake induced disturbance generated through a finite element analysis on the M2 mirror for ELT. The simulations have been set up in SPECULA [11], an end-to-end Adaptive Optics simulator, in a simplified framework, involving a single Natural Guide Star (NGS) on-axis, the effect of propagation through the atmosphere and a tip-tilt deformable mirror, at a sampling frequency of 500 Hz. No high-frequency modes have been involved in the simulation, and measurement noise has been artificially added on the reconstructed modes, without considering the effect of a detector. It should be noted that, if other colored noise signals are present, the same approach described in this work can be extended by identifying the noise filtering dynamics and extending the state-space, minimizing the overall resulting disturbance. In the data history considered for the simulations, the tilt signal was dominant, so the optimization approach was applied to the tilt channel. The same overall IIR filter has then been adopted for both tip and tilt channels.

Figure 5. Comparison of steady-state RMS in different noise conditions

Figure 6. History of the optimized gain at each optimization interval (noise variance: 60).

Figure 7. Optimal gain as a function of the measurement noise standard deviation.

Figure 8. Time history of the residuals (noise variance: 60)

In figure 5, a comparison is shown between the residual variance obtained with different fixed gain values and the optimized gain computed both through the offline and online approaches, solving (27). The admissible range for the gain was set to $[0, 1]$, which is a reasonable bound based on the 2 samples loop delay of the simulated loop. For the online optimization, an interval of 1 seconds has been considered ($K = 500$) between successive resolutions of the optimization problem. At each resolution, the full past data of wind-shake induced tip-tilt has been used, assuming that the open-loop disturbance is available or reconstructable. An initial guess for the optimal gain was set to $g = 0.5$ in all configurations. In figure 6, the sequence of optimal computed gains in the 60 noise standard deviation case is reported. The results show the effectiveness of the optimization approach as a practical alternative to the manual tuning of the gain for each noise configuration. The performance of the online and offline optimization approaches is comparable, as expected from a short simulation interval in which observation conditions do not change significantly. As input from the user, the expected noise standard deviation is required, which may be related to the magnitude of the natural guide star, and the overall loop delay. The online optimization approach may be effective in long observations during which the conditions may vary, but is limited by the need for an accurate open-loop data reconstruction. In figure 7, an analysis is reported, showing the optimal offline computed gains for the tilt channel as a function of the noise standard deviation. As the noise amplitude increases, the optimal gain decreases, as the bandwidth of the IIR filter needs to be reduced to mitigate noise amplification. Finally, in figure 8, the time history of the tip-tilt residuals is shown for the configuration with noise variance 60.

7. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we presented a gain optimization strategy for tip-tilt correction in Adaptive Optics systems designed for Extremely Large Telescopes. The proposed optimization framework allows for dynamic tuning of the regulator transfer function to minimize residual wavefront error variance in closed-loop. The gain optimization is performed

through the resolution of a quadratic constrained optimization problem in the time-domain. Two formulations of the optimization problem have been tested, one in finite-horizon, suited for online optimization of the regulator in a scenario in which a-priori knowledge of the disturbance characteristics is not available, and one in infinite-horizon, suited for offline optimization of the regulator when a sufficiently informative history of disturbance data is available. The optimization approach is flexible enough to allow for the enrichment of the model with noise propagation in the loop, enabling proper tuning of the regulator in different observation scenarios. The performance of the proposed approach has been tested on SPECULA in a minimalistic framework.

Future steps will involve comparing the approach with the well-known approach in [5], and extending the optimization to more complex scenarios, involving higher-order modes, and more complex noise sources. The approach may also be extended to optimize other parameters of the IIR filters, for example, to shape the sensitivity function in the presence of higher-order uncompensated modes or to include some adaptation properties to combine the infinite horizon and finite horizon approaches, initializing the exosystem dynamics with some a-priori knowledge and then changing the model adaptively with online data. The main limitation of the online approach lies in the reconstruction of the open-loop data for training. In presence of higher-order modes, non-linearities in the WFS response, and other noise sources, the reconstruction of the open-loop data for training may be a complex task. The offline gain optimization of the gain only relies on a-priori knowledge on the system and the exogenous dynamics, making its application straight-forward in experimental scenarios. In fact, the optimization approach is compatible with the implementation on the real-time computer of MORFEO [2], both in its offline formulation and in the online receding horizon approach, tuning the optimization frequency based on the system functional frequency, which may vary based on the NGS magnitude.

References

- [1] Richard P Brent. *Algorithms for minimization without derivatives*. Courier Corporation, 2013.
- [2] Giulio Capasso et al. “MORFEO at ELT: recent updates in the real-time computer design”. In: *Software and Cyberinfrastructure for Astronomy VIII*. Vol. 13101. SPIE. 2024, pp. 1328–1342.
- [3] Paolo Ciliegi et al. “MORFEO at ELT: the adaptive optics module for ELT”. In: *Adaptive Optics Systems IX*. Vol. 13097. SPIE. 2024, pp. 539–548.
- [4] *Data package for ELT simulations*. Tech. rep. ESO-315732.
- [5] Eric Gendron and Pierre Léna. “Astronomical adaptive optics. 1: Modal control optimization”. In: *Astronomy and Astrophysics (ISSN 0004-6361), vol. 291, no. 1, p. 337-347* 291 (1994), pp. 337–347.
- [6] Roberto Gilmozzi and Jason Spyromilio. “The European Extremely Large Telescope (E-ELT)”. In: *The Messenger*. Vol. 127. 2007, pp. 11–19.
- [7] Sebastian Iglesias et al. “Wind shake and telescope vibrations: impact on image quality”. In: *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society* 511.3 (2022), pp. 3589–3602.
- [8] Caroline Kulcsár et al. “Optimal control, observers and integrators in adaptive optics”. In: *Optics express* 14.17 (2006), pp. 7464–7476.
- [9] Brice Le Roux et al. “Optimal control law for classical and multiconjugate adaptive optics”. In: *Journal of the Optical Society of America A* 21.7 (2004), pp. 1261–1276.
- [10] Douglas G MacMynowski et al. “Wind loads on ground-based telescopes”. In: *Applied optics* 45.30 (2006), pp. 7912–7923.
- [11] Fabio Rossi, Alfio Puglisi, and Guido Agapito. “Introducing a new generation adaptive optics simulation framework: from PASSATA to SPECULA”. In: *Journal of Astronomical Telescopes, Instruments, and Systems* 12.1 (2026), p. 019001. DOI: [10.1117/1.JATIS.12.1.019001](https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JATIS.12.1.019001). URL: <https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JATIS.12.1.019001>.
- [12] Babak Sedghi, M Müller, and M Dimmler. “Analyzing the impact of vibrations on E-ELT primary segmented mirror”. In: *Modeling, Systems Engineering, and Project Management for Astronomy VII*. Vol. 9911. SPIE. 2016, pp. 403–413.
- [13] Roberto Tamai et al. “The E-ELT construction”. In: *Proceedings of SPIE* 9906 (2016), 99060W.